

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Low numbers of earthworms in agricultural fields pose a significant threat to soil health and crop productivity

Intensive farming practices, including excessive pesticide and fertilizer use, deep ploughing, and monocropping, have led to a decline in earthworm populations. This reduction results in decreased soil porosity, reduced water infiltration, and impaired microbial activity, making soils less fertile. Consequently, crop yields decline, and the soil becomes more prone to erosion and nutrient depletion, increasing the need for artificial fertilizers and further exacerbating environmental degradation.

1. Earthworms are abundantly present in undisturbed, organic-rich soils (ILVO).

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

Agro-ecological farming and the use of grass silage as organic fertilizer positively impact earthworm numbers

Case-study 9 followed an agro-ecological farming system that included no soil tillage or reduced tillage without conversion, combined with the application of organic matter as fertilizer. Main crops were sown or planted manually, and no herbicides, pesticides, or other chemicals were used. A cover crop was cultivated between the main crops and incorporated into the soil after its destruction. These practices help restore earthworm populations. Our results show that grass silage was the only source of organic fertilizer to demonstrate a clear increase in

earthworm numbers. These findings suggest that grass silage may serve as a particularly suitable food source for earthworms, potentially supporting their development more effectively than farmyard manure or compost. Indeed, earthworms thrive on decomposing organic matter, and silage, being partially fermented, can be easier for them to digest than fresh plant material. However, attention must be given to factors such as pH, moisture content, nutrient balance, and the risk of molding.

2. Grass silage was produced by fermenting grass that was cut at the early flowering stage under airtight conditions (POMONA).

3. Grass silage was applied to the field as an organic fertilizer (POMONA).

4. Box plots of the number of earthworms counted in soil samples treated with different sources of organic fertilizer from 2021 till 2023. GS = grass silage, compost = composted brown organic material, FYM = farmyard manure, none = control without organic fertilizer (ILVO).

KEYWORDS

Agro-ecological farming, earthworm numbers, grass silage, organic fertilizer.

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